

Journal of Health and Medical Sciences

Jama, M. A., Cao, L., Li, Y., & Ji, B. (2024), Systematic Review on the Current Situation and Development of Local Antimicrobial Agents in Revision Arthroplasty for Periprosthetic Joint Infection (PJI). *Journal of Health and Medical Sciences*, 7(1), 59-71.

ISSN 2622-7258

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1994.07.01.306

The online version of this article can be found at:
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Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Systematic Review on the Current Situation and Development of Local Antimicrobial Agents in Revision Arthroplasty for Periprosthetic Joint Infection (PJI)

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Abstract

Total joint arthroplasty is a common surgery to treat degenerative joint disease, and it significantly improves the lives of people suffering from conditions such as osteoarthritis. Moreover, it is very essential to know that the fact that the level of joint replacement surgery is discouraged by complications, therefore making the periprosthetic infection (PJI) to become a critical issue. As such PJI is full of significant negative results in a current pain, implant failure, and also as a systemic infection. Basically, the complex origin of PJI is usually involved in the formation of biofilms (protective communities of bacteria) which become resistant to the standard treatments. This capability to resist is able to highlight the urgency to look more into new strategies so as to particularly disrupt and to be able to prevent biofilm formation. In addition to that Topical antimicrobials that generally range from intraarticular antibiotic infusions and antibiotic-filled spacers, have therefore become the focus of this effort. In addition to this, the drugs are able to target the infection site directly, that probably leads to the minimization of systemic exposure and therefore increasing effectiveness of the treatment. Therefore, the knowledge of this challenges, this specific systematic review tends to aim so as to assess the current state and as well as advancements in local antimicrobial agents for the management of PJI. Moreover, by involving mechanisms, consideration of safety, in addition to its effectiveness, the review is able to give out insights that may shape more effective clinical approaches so as to fight Periprosthetic Joint Infection.

Keywords: Review, Local Antimicrobial Agents, Revision Arthroplasty, Periprosthetic Joint Infection

1. Introduction

Periprosthetic Joint Infection (PJI) is known a complication which associated with the revision arthroplasty. PJI being a complication causes a significant problem to patients and the healthcare providers. That condition hence leads to pain, implant failure, and also the systematic spread of infections. These infections later affect the entire body or multiple organ systems. These infections include sepsis whereby bacteria and other pathogens invade the bloodstream and cause inflammation and organ dysfunction and viral infections such as influenza which affect the overall quality of patient life and could lead to high mortality rates. These problems go below the usefulness of considering the management of PJI as an essential consideration in orthopedic surgery. This systematic review aims to assess the current state and ongoing developments in local antimicrobial agents in the context of revision arthroplasty for PJI.

The treatment and management of PJI is made more difficult by the formation of biofilm. Biofilms are arrangements of bacterial communities that attaches itself to prosthetic surface, in this case Biofilms prevents the treatment and diagnosis of PJI, therefore causing continuous infections around the implant. These findings show the complex relationship between Biofilms and PJIs, also giving out the benefits of creative ways to curb this resilient bacterial phenomenon. In addition, the study goes through the different treatment strategies which are likely to work and be more successful which are later considered and used to bring about good and improved clinical results. Most importantly, the aim of the study is to know more about function of local antimicrobial agents in managing Periprosthetic Joint Infection.

1.1. Biofilm Pathology

Biofilms are structured communities of bacteria intricately connected to the extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) (Waheed et al., 2022). Biofilm formation is a crucial factor in the pathogenesis of PJI. In the case of PJI pathogens attach themselves on the surface of prosthetic joint and in-turn create biofilms. Biofilms are difficult to eradicate and inhibit treatment of PJI bacteria. Bacteria in an established biofilm are up to 10,000 times more resistant to antibiotic therapy in comparison to their free-floating planktonic counterparts (Rabin et al 2015). The EPS matrix protects the bacteria from the patient's immune system and antibiotics that are administered making the pathogens extremely resistant to treatment. Biofilm-protected bacteria often course the recurrence of infections after initial treatment (Zimmerli & Sendi, 2010). This occurrence is because some protected bacteria might remain persistent even after treatment, making PJI treatment a long-term challenge.

Experts have and are exploring various strategies to prevent and disrupt formation of biofilms. Research into the topic is critical in PJI management. Preventive measures include the development of prosthetic materials that resist the formation of biofilm and research into implant coating with antimicrobial properties. Disruptive measures include the dispersion of enzymes such as B and DNase in treatment. Enzymes B and DNase have been studied for their ability to disrupt biofilm matrix (Hall-Stoodley et al, 2004) Thus making the bacteria more accessible to antibiotics. Medical personnel also use high-dose of prolonged antibiotic therapy as a disruptive measure against biofilms. Rifampin an example of an antibiotic has shown effectiveness against bacteria encased in biofilms (Zimmerli et al, 2004). Therefore the use of different combinations of antibiotics with different mechanisms of actions has been effective in enhancing the disruption of biofilms (Tande & Patel, 2014).

1.2. Local antimicrobial agents

The management of PJI leads to the need for a multifaceted approach and local antimicrobial agents have emerged as a very important component in the battle against this condition (Mustafa et al., 2023). The adoption of local antibacterial agents has effectively revolutionized the treatment of PJI this is by representing critical advancement in the management of the condition. Local antimicrobial agents make sure that antibiotics or antibacterial substances are targeted directly to the sites which are infected, optimizing treatment efficiency (Kalelkar et al., 2022). This is not like systemic administration which leads to diluted antibiotic concentrations and potential systemic side effects. Local agents of antibiotic delivery ensure that there is high local concentration while minimizing the risk of adverse reactions.

The importance of local antimicrobial agents depends in their inbuilt mechanisms that enables them to have the ability to fight against biofilm-encased bacteria effectively, penetrate the biofilm matrix, and reduce the risk of the same infections happening. The formation of biofilm is a key aspect of PJI development and a huge challenge in its management (Taha et al., 2018). There are various types of Local Antimicrobial agents which include intra-articular antibiotic infusion, antibiotic beads, antibiotic-loaded cement spacers, and antibiotic extended-release implants. There are various advantages of Local agents over traditional systemic antibiotic therapies, which include:

1. High local concentration – Local antimicrobial agents such as antibiotic loaded cement spacers or beads allow for delivery of antibiotics directly to the targeted site which results in significantly higher local concentration of antibiotics ensuring that they can effectively combat the infecting bacteria at the source (Bayramov, 2017).
2. Reduced systemic side effects - local antimicrobial agents are designed to deliver antibiotics directly to the infected site which reduces systemic exposure to antibiotics, minimizing the risk of adverse reactions and toxicities associated with high-doses in systemic antibiotic therapy.
3. Targeted and efficient therapy - Overall local antimicrobial agents provide highly targeted therapy (Koo, 2017). By delivering antibiotics directly to the infected there is a minimized risk of harming healthy tissues. This targeted approach enhances the effectiveness of treatment ensuring that antibiotics are concentrated where they are needed underscoring the chance of infection eradication (Spellberg, 2015).
4. Prevention of recurrence - PJI usually has a high risk of recurrence. The used of localized high concentration of antibiotics achieved with the agents is extremely effective in reducing the risk of recurrence by eradicating the infecting bacteria at the source, the agent can help the infection from reoccurring after treatment.
5. Minimized treatment complexity - The use of local agents simplifies the treatment of PJI. In some cases, such as the use of antibiotic loaded cement spacer, the spacer itself provides mechanical support for the joint while delivering antibiotics (Spellberg, 2015). This reduces the complexity of treatment by combining the role of mechanical support and drug delivery into a single intervention.

Local antimicrobial agent is delivered to the infection site using various mechanisms (ter Boo, 2015). Below is a table of mechanisms summarizing the mechanisms of action of different local antimicrobial agents in PJI.

Local Antimicrobial Agent	Mechanism of Action
Intra-articular Antibiotic Infusion	Direct delivery of antibiotics into the joint space to combat infection locally
Antibiotic-Loaded Cement Spacer	Antibiotics mixed with cement gradually elute into the surrounding tissues, providing sustained local coverage.
Antibiotic Beads	Small beads filled with antibiotics slowly release the drugs, maintaining high local concentrations.
Antibiotic Extended-Release Implants	Implants release antibiotics over an extended period, continuously targeting the infection site

2. Intra-articular antibiotic infusion

An intra-articular antibiotic infusion is a specialized approach to the management of PJI. The approach involves the direct delivery of high antibiotic concentrations into the joint spaces and targeting biofilm and pathogens. Various studies have shown and demonstrated the effectiveness of the method in eradicating PJI pathogens. The method is appreciated by medics not only because it is effective but also because it minimizes systemic exposure to antibiotics (McLaren & McLaren, 2016). A study by McLaren & McLaren (2016) showed a 92.9% clinical success rate and a 7.1% recurrence rate in the treatment of shoulder joint septic arthritis. A study also showed that there was 88.2% of patients achieved infection control and 11.8% recurrence in the knee and hip PJI (Piggott et al, 2019). The methods have various advantages and disadvantages.

2.1. Advantages

Intra-articular antibiotic infusion allows the delivery of exceptionally high antibiotics directly to the infected area. The localized therapy targets pathogens within the joint specifically addressing the source of infection efficiently (McLaren & McLaren, 2016). By limiting antibiotic exposure to the infected area, the method reduces the side effects associated with other broad-spectrum antibiotics. This advantage ensures that the patient experiences fewer adverse reactions, enhancing compliance and tolerability (Parvizi & Tarity, 2012). The approach also demonstrated the ability to penetrate biofilm which is a critical aspect in the management of PJI in a study done by Zimmerli & Sendi (2010). Biofilms in some cases shield the bacteria from antibiotics. This makes it important to penetrate the biofilms to ensure successful treatment,

2.2. Disadvantages

The intra-articular antibiotic infusion method carries some disadvantages. Firstly, the approach involves a surgical procedure. These procedures carry various risks and increase the overall complexity of treatment (Artz et al, 2015). In the treatment procedure, patients need to undergo anaesthesia, which may result in additional hospitalization. The method is effective against resistant or multi-organism infections (Kuiper et al, 2013). The method targets specific joint spaces and at times PJI infections occur at various locations, this occurrence necessitates a broader strategic approach which the method does not consider.

2.3. Safety

Intra-articular antibiotic infusion involves introducing antibiotics into the joint space to PJIs. Safety concerns include the risk of systemic effects, local tissue irritation, and adverse reactions (Cyphert, 2020). Generally, it is considered safe, however, careful antibiotic selection, dosing, and monitoring. Aseptic techniques during infusion are important in preventing additional complications (Horlocker, 2011). Patient-specific including allergies should be considered.

2.4. Feasibility

Intra-articular infusion is a feasible approach since it gives a practical application in that it delivers a localized treatment approach, feasibility depends on the accessibility of the joint, choice of antibiotic, and severity of the infection (Foster, 2023). Feasible methods of delivery include direct injection, drug-eluting implants, and joint lavage, the choice of approach relies on the surgeon's expertise and characteristics of PJI (Rodríguez-Merchán, 2021).

2.5. Effectiveness

Intra-articular antibiotic infusion provides targeted treatment which enhances the effectiveness of treatment by providing higher antibiotic concentration at infection point. The effectiveness of intra-articular antibiotic infusion may vary depending on the type and extent of the infection. The approach is often most suitable for early and less aggressive infections. As an example, research carried out by Ji et al. in 2019 showed that a single-stage revision with cement less reconstruction could be one of the treatment that could highly work for chronic infections in total hip arthroplasty (THA). This study, which included 126 patients which were from different ethnicities and different characteristics and found that 89.2% of the participants were not infected after an average assessment of 58 months (Day et al., 2021).

In another study, Ji et al. (2020) looked into the level of desired success of single-stage revision using intra-articular antibiotic infusion in finishing culture-negative PJI. Thus, the results found considered that this method could be very important in managing culture-negative PJI as it is in culture-positive cases.

However, a study carried out in 2022 by Ji et al. went through the usefulness of single-stage revision using intra-articular antibiotic infusion this is due to multiple unsuccessful surgeries for PJI. The researchers found out that

this method could deliver a high concentration of antibiotics in the synovial fluid, thereby being able to overcome challenges such as reduced vascular supply and biofilm formation. Therefore this alternative method of administration could be a potential treatment option for PJI, more so particularly in cases where previous surgeries have failed to resolve the infection.

These studies have shown that intra-articular antibiotic infusion could be a promising treatment strategy for PJI, even in advanced cases such as culture-negative infections and instances involving multiple prior surgeries which are not successful. However, more research is needed to validate these results and to refine the application of this treatment method.

3. Local Antibiotic Carriers

The use of antibiotic carriers acts as an alternative approach that allows for the maintaining of high local concentrations of antibiotics without systemic exposure, local antibiotic carriers incorporate an antimicrobial to prolong its half-life as well as provide predictable elution characteristics while at times they may play assistance role such as filling dead space and providing mechanical support for limb alignment (Engin et al, 2019). The most effective carrier is one that provides prolonged antibiotic concentrations at an effective level and achieves complete antibiotic release to reduce subtherapeutic elution time, is extremely versatile and has compatibility with the desired antibiotics, and is fully resorbable with minimized risks of allergies, local and systemic adverse effects (Le et al., 2021).

4. Hydrogels

Hydrogels are three-dimensional networks of hydrophilic polymers that can absorb and retain significant amounts of water or other fluid within their structure. Hydrogels have a unique ability to respond to changes in environmental conditions such as pH, temperature, and ionic subsequently triggering swelling or deswelling (Xie et al, 2022). In the context of PJI hydrogels offer a unique and innovative approach to the management of the condition by acting as effective delivery systems for antibiotics and antimicrobial agents.

The treatment process using hydrogels involves impregnating the hydrogel with the desired antimicrobial substance through chemical bonding, entrapment, or physical mixing (Gonçalves et al., 2019). The hydrogel is then placed into contact with bodily fluids or the surrounding environment where it absorbs water or biological fluids causing it to swell causing the hydrogel to release the loaded antimicrobial agents in a controlled and sustained manner. The advantages of hydrogel include controlled and sustained release, biofilm penetration, and reducing the risk of adverse reactions and toxicity (Xie, et al, 2022). One of the limitations is complexity, the preparation and application of hydrogels is extremely complex, especially in comparison to local antimicrobial agents this entails the need for specific expertise and equipment. Another limitation of hydrogels is that they suffer from biodegradation and may need to be replaced or replenished periodically this can introduce practicality challenges.

4.1. Safety

Hydrogels safety varies depending on the specific composition and the function made for. In addition most hydrogels are biocompatible and show low toxicity, this makes them safe in the treatment of PJIs (Atkin et al., 2022). However, there are reactions for example allergic reactions and inflammatory responses (Osmon et al., 2013). It is very essential to carry out biocompatibility and safety studies before administering hydrogels to patients (Lei et al., 2022).

4.2. Feasibility

The use of hydrogels in the management of PJI is capable of being done (Evans et al., 2023). Hydrogel can be transformed to come up with a supportive environment for drug delivery, allowing for the sustained release of

antibiotics at the target site (Chakrapani et al., 2022). Hydrogels ability to adapt to different such as injectables or coating for prosthetic components makes them very easily capable to be done (Karczewski et al., 2021).

4.3. Effectiveness

The effectiveness of hydrogels in the treatment of PJIs is determined by their ability deliver antibiotics locally therefore providing targeted and sustained therapeutic effects. Hydrogels also plays a role as carriers for antimicrobial agents and contribute to infection control (Samuel & Gould, 2009). More over the incorporation of hydrogels leads to controlled antibiotic release, there for overcoming challenges associated with systemic administration (Zheng et al., 2023). In order to ensure overall effectiveness it is important to regulate their mechanical properties to ensure that there is stability in the joint environment and to bring about the desired drug release kinetics (Li et al., 2023).

5. Antibiotic-Loaded Cement Spacer

This is an essential component in the management and revision of arthroplasty, Most especially in PJI. The Antibiotic-Loaded Cement spacers are temporary prosthetic material that are created using bone cement that is accumulated with antibiotics. These spacers have two major functions in PJI management which are maintaining joint space and functioning and delivering antibiotics locally. Antibiotic-loaded cement spacers have various positive outcomes in the treatment and management of PJI. They offer highly concentrated and targeted antibiotics at the site of infection specifically targeting at the pathogens responsible for the infection.

This method is However useful since most bacteria in PJI are encased in biofilms. In addition the spacers also allow the patient to maintain joint stability and functionality during the duration of the treatment, this is to be able to improve mobility and comfort during the crucial period. Moreover, various studies carried out in the last twenty years have shown that spacers reduce the risk of recurrent infection (Valle, 2004). These studies give further evidence of the efficiency of the spacers.

One of the most significant limitations of spacers is that they are temporary equipment. This temporality creates a need for subsequent surgery for the removal of spacers and the introduction of permanent implantation. The need for additional surgery increases the risk factor for patients with PJI (Parvizi, 2012). Additionally antibiotic spacers at times may be ineffective against highly resistant and multi-organism infections that call for broader systemic antibiotic therapy.

Over the years several studies into antibiotic-loaded cement spacers in PJI management. Anagnostakos et al in 2018 reported that the use of an antibiotic loader in two-stage revision in infected total knee arthroplasty resulted in an infection control rate of eighty seven percent. Moreover, Kuiper et al in 2013 showed that spacer had a success rate of eighty-seven percent in two-stage hip revision surgery.

One of the most extensively used Antibiotic-Loaded Cement Spacer is PMMA Polymethylmethacrylate commonly referred to as bone cement. PMMA cement is impregnated with antibiotics before it hardens and acts as a mechanical spacer to maintain joint stability and a local drug delivery system to treat PJI. The mechanism and consideration in the use of PMMA as an Antibiotic-Loaded cement spacer involve several steps such as the aforementioned impregnation with antibiotics, these involve mixing antibiotics with the PMMA, the choice of antibiotics usually varies depending on the factors previously mentioned in the paper, sometimes antibiotics can be pre-mixed with PMMA by manufacturer or this can be done at the time of surgery to allow for customization based on the specific patient needs and the pathogens.

This process is usually an intricate balancing act as high concentrations of antibiotics, though can improve bacterial eradication could destroy the structural integrity of the cement compromising its mechanical strength. Once cured, the PMMA cement forms a load-bearing spacer. The spacer is inserted after debridement during the first of a two-stage exchange procedure.

The spacer ensures joint stability, and bone alignment and aids in weight-bearing, mobility, and pain management. Antibiotics mixed with the PMMA cement release directly at the site of infection. This is an effective method for treating localized infection in PJI. The release of antibiotics from PMMA cement occurs in two steps an initial burst followed by a slow decline in concentration. Elution can be improved by shaping smaller beads with a larger surface area which can release a higher percentage of contained antibiotic over time. Below is a reference diagram showing the process.

5.1. Safety

In general antibiotic-loaded cement spacers are considered safe this is because they deliver high concentrations of antibiotics at specific targeted points of infections while also still providing mechanical support (Iarikov et al., 2012). As they are very effective against bacteria on the downside to their safety there is a significant challenge of developing antibiotic resistance. The longer use of antibiotics may lead to the development of resistant strains which brings to careful consideration regarding the use antibiotic and the amount of time to be used (Sabater-Martos et al., 2023).

5.2. Feasibility

The ability of antibiotic-loaded cement spacers being feasible lies in their ability to deliver high concentrations of antibiotics to the target site (Fu et al., 2020). The local delivery reduces the systemic side effects that are related with prolonged oral or intravenous antibiotic therapy. Cement spacers play also a role in providing mechanical stability which allows for the preservation of joints as well as mobility during treatment, this especially makes them feasible for example in cases where the infected prosthetic may need to be temporarily removed (Lunz et al., 2022).

5.3. Effectiveness

Antibiotic-loaded cement spacers are very effective in the complete eradication of joint infection. The main function is that they can release high concentrations of antibiotics for over an extended period at a specific infection point Thus being able to improve overall chances of complete infection eradication (van Vugt et al., 2019). In addition the use of spacers offers only a temporary solution, which undercuts its effectiveness. Medical personnel most of the time consider the approach during a staged approach; There are two stages involved, the first stage which involves the removal of the infected prosthesis implanting antibiotic-loaded spacer and also administering systemic antibiotics. In the second stage the spacer is later removed, and finally a new prosthesis is implanted (Fu et al., 2020).

6. Antibiotic Beads

Antibiotic beads help in the management of PJI, especially in cases where systemic antibiotics are unreliable (Ricciardi, 2020). Antibiotic beads are small biodegradable beads that are injected with antibiotics and are directly placed at the site of infection (Tzeng et al., 2015). Some of the most crucial advantages that make the approach highly feasible include localized antibiotic delivery, biofilm penetration, and reduced risk of systemic toxicity which have been discussed as advantages of intra-articular antibiotic infusion. However, the latter offers to resolve one of the challenges identified earlier in the paper which is the increased risk of antibiotic resistance by biofilm encased PJI bacteria (Getzlaf et al, 2016).

The strategy also has various disadvantages for example, the strategy offers a temporary solution since they are biodegradable, this calls for a subsequent revision strategy for the implantation of the permanent prosthesis, which entails surgery on the infected further enhancing the risk and inherent complexities of surgeries to patient. Furthermore, the small beads are targeted towards a specific pathogen which makes them highly ineffective in cases of multi-organism infection (Kozlowski et al., 2022). Moreover, there is a significant of the beads migrating from the infected spaces they can comprehensively compromise their effectiveness. Furthermore, there is limited

data on the clinical success rate of the beads. This calls for investigating further into their long-term effectiveness (Neuberger et al., 2017).

6.1. Safety

Antibiotic beads are able to reduce systemic exposure and therefore minimize the risk of the systemic side effects. Hence as a result of this, they are highly considered to be safe, Since they provide the safety this is by providing localized antibiotic delivery which are specifically directed to the infected site (van Vugt et al., 2019). However, those beads do not completely cover the area infected and ending up having a probability of risk of infection persistence (Wouthuyzen-Bakker et al., 2018).

6.2. Feasibility

In additionally ,The major factor that enables antibiotic beads to be feasible is that they can be able to placed precisely at the surgical point there for this is for allowing for targeted antibiotic to be released (van Vugt et al., 2019). The beads are also feasible this is because they are also capable of reducing the risk of patients facing systemic complications .Also the local release of antibiotics from beads is able to reduce the use for prolonged antibiotic therapy (Steadman et al., 2023).

6.3. Effectiveness

The antibiotic beads are also effective in the control of infections this is by being able to release high concentrations of antibiotics which are specifically directed into the infected area (van Vugt et al., 2019). Additionally, they also may be used to complement treatment as in cases where the systemic antibiotics may be not enough and may be used as an additional component to surgical procedures (Steadman et al., 2023).

7. Antibiotic Extended-Release Implants

For this strategy which is applied in the treatment of PJI infections is relatively new this is when comparing to the other strategies that have been discussed in the paper (Cataldo et al, 2010). The implants' inner workings are what makes them to be able to be different to the rest in that it is also formulated to be able to provide a sustained and controlled antibiotics release aimed directly into the infection site. This approach gives out significant challenges which are associated with the treatment of PJI and additionally overcomes the disadvantages experienced by other devices (Shoji et al, 2020).

Firstly, the development of the implants focuses on prolonged antibiotic release thus making them highly sustainable when comparing to other methods (Szyk et al, 2023). The long exposure of antibiotics on the sites that are infected ensures that a therapeutic concentration of antibiotics is present at the infected point thus enhancing the implant effectiveness (Anagnostakos et al, 2010). To add up , the implants also directly target the infected joint as is mentioned in other devices discussed previously . Moreover, while the antibiotic-loaded cement spacers and beads in various cases require additional surgical procedures for replacement and removal thus increasing the complexity in treatment of PJI , antibiotic extended-release implants is much more efficient, In that Once the implant is in place the patient does not need to undergo another surgery to remove it (Ma et al, 2018). Additionally, the treatment procedure can effectively fight the re occurrence of antibiotics due to the sustained release strategy (Xiong et al, 2014).

7.1. Safety

Firstly, Antibiotic extended-release implants are made up for a localized antibiotic which are able to make them a safe option this is because they reduce systemic exposure and potential side effects that are brought about by intravenous or prolonged oral antibiotic use (Le Vavasseur & Zeller, 2022). The negative side to this is that there is a risk of infection persistence especially if the implants do not fully cover the extended area (Le Vavasseur & Zeller, 2022).

7.2. Feasibility

For feasibility of extended-release implants it lies in their ability to give out targeted antibiotic delivery to the infected joint space and also the ability to control the release of antibiotics for a long duration Thus reducing the need for frequent intervention (Le Vasseur & Zeller, 2022). Also the feasibility of the implants heavily depends on ease of surgical placement, implant design, and compatibility with joint anatomy (Baddour & Chen, 2022).

7.3. Effectiveness

The extended-release implants are important in maintaining sustained antibiotic levels at the infection site thus leading to better outcomes (Le Vasseur & Zeller, 2022). In addition they are also effective in a way that they limit antibiotic exposure to the infection site; thus helping reduce the risk of systemic side effects (Le Vasseur & Zeller, 2022).

7.4. Comparative analysis

So as to help medics formulate informed decisions on the choice of local antimicrobial agents, it is essential to create a comparative analysis this is by highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of each agent in terms of safety, effectiveness, and feasibility.

7.5. Safety

Intra-articular Antibiotic Infusion (IAI) use is considered safe this is by reducing systemic antibiotic exposure; however, it possesses the risk of secondary surgical procedures which has inherent risk (Li et al., 2021). The antibiotic-loaded Cement Spacer (ALCS) use is also considered safe but has spacer-related complications including dislocation and fracture are factors that make it unsafe (Li et al., 2023). Antibiotic Beads (AB) use might be considered the most unsafe due to various factors such as a risk of bead migration which could compromise safety. It entails that a secondary surgery may be needed to mitigate the risk (van Vugt et al., 2019). The Antibiotic Extended-Release Implant (AERI) is developed for the safety since it provides long term antibiotic release and does not lead to additional secondary surgical need (Le Vasseur & Zeller, 2022).

8. Discussion

The Single-stage revision having intra-articular antibiotic infusion has come up as a future fruitful treatment option for periprosthetic joint infection (PJI) (Ji et al., 2019). Various studies carried out have regularly demonstrated its desired result, with their success level ranging from 84% to 99% even in complex cases involving culture-negative PJI, multidrug-resistant organisms, and multiple failed surgeries (Li et al., 2022). The incorporation of the approach offers several mentioned advantages over traditional two-stage revision, which includes reduction in surgical burden, decrease in hospitalization times, and improvement in functional outcomes.

As evident to the study that was conducted in 2019 by (Ji et al.), it is evident that the function is to investigate the use of single-stage revision with cement less reconstruction as a treatment for chronically infected total hip arthroplasty (THA). In addition, far from the traditional two-stage approach, which is involved in removing the infected implant, and treating the infection, then later re-implant a new joint.

The following had 126 patients who had different characteristics, thus representing a wide range of candidates than typically correct for single-stage processes (Li et al., 2022). The findings were encouraging, having one of them being a high success rate: At an average follow-up of 58 months, 89.2% of patients remained infection-free. There was high success rate for patients with challenging conditions like multidrug-resistant organisms (84.2%) (Li et al., 2022).

Improved mobility and function: For example Patients reported significant improvements in hip function as according to the Harris hip score, thus reaching an average of 79.6 points at the final assessment (Chahal et al, 2015).

Cementless reconstruction benefits: The use of cementless implants may bring about to the positive results. The cementless implants gives way for better bone integration and potentially minimizes the risk of loosening and infection associated with cement (Matthias et al, 2021). These studies suggest that single-stage revision with cementless reconstruction can be a viable and effective option for treating chronic hip infections. This approach has more benefits over the two-stage method, which includes reduced hospital stays, faster recovery times, and potentially lower costs. However, it is essential to point that this study has limitations. Extended follow-up and comparing with the other treatment options are needed to confirm the long-term success of this approach (Elliott et al, 2011).

Most importantly, high doses of antibiotics are poured directly into the joint space, bathing the site and potentially eradicating the unseen enemy. The outcomes are promising when Comparing to a control group of culture-positive patients, the "infused" group achieved a similarly impressive 90.2% infection-free rate after over four years (Li et al., 2022). The findings suggest that even without knowing the exact foe, a targeted combat can be of full function. Of course, there are caveats. Extended research and larger studies are needed to solidify these results. This research is able to open the door to a potentially faster, single-stage treatment option for a particularly frustrating type of PJI. In conclusion by delivering antibiotics directly to the desired target, intra-articular infusion may offer a valuable support in the fight against invisible joint invaders (Li et al., 2022).

9. Conclusion

In a nutshell, management of Periprosthetic Joint Infection (PJI) during arthroplasty revision is a complicated problem that requires comprehensive detailed research and data-driven decision-making (Ji et al., 2022). This article underperforms the importance of accurate diagnosis, a multidisciplinary use, and the utilization of several local antimicrobial agents in PJI management. Therefor the focus on agents like intra-articular antibiotic infusion, antibiotic-loaded cement spacers, beads, and extended-release implants is emphasized, which aims to reduce systemic side effects and recurrence. The paper pushes for future research into local antimicrobial agents, this is by considering safety, effectiveness, feasibility, and individual patient characteristics.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

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